

THE IMPORTANCE OF EMOTIONAL INTELLIGENCE IN THE WORK OF THE MANAGER OF AN EDUCATIONAL ORGANIZATION AND WAYS TO IMPROVE IT

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ABSTRACT

The article offers a general overview of the role of emotional intelligence in a manager's work, as well as ways to enhance it. Emotional intelligence is a kind of "ability", and implies social and professional competencies that allow a person to successfully communicate and interact with others. From all this it follows that emotional intelligence should be compared with the competencies that are necessary for personal development and career growth. Emotional intelligence, as an alternative to traditional intelligence, has become widely popular in psychological and pedagogical science. This concept is in the spotlight for a reason, emotional intelligence has a good potential for practical application in addressing both personal development and career growth, as well as effective management of the personnel of an educational organization. In this article, we applied the EQ measurement technique - Hall test, which provides the most comprehensive assessment of personality traits that characterize emotional abilities. The article also presents the five characteristics of emotional intelligence according to Goleman (knowledge of our emotions, self-motivation, management of our emotions, empathy, and the ability to manage relationships). Two Larsen models that help to explain how emotional intelligence works are discussed.

Keywords: emotional intelligence, manager, human resource management, education, emotion management, educational organization.

Introduction

Today, the Republic of Kazakhstan pays special attention to education. President of the Republic of Kazakhstan Kassym-Jomart Tokayev tries to create all conditions for quality education, formation and development of personality of each citizen. Therefore, special attention is paid to the heads of educational organizations of Kazakhstan, as the main goal of the state is to educate a person with an active life position, as a citizen of the republic and its patriot.

Today in the Kazakhstani society the issues of managerial activity become the most urgent. The President of Kazakhstan Kassym-Jomart Tokayev noted at the plenary session of Majilis in January 2022: "The system of public administration needs a complex reform. The principle of meritocracy should become a real principle of recruitment and promotion. Public service should be open to any Kazakhstani" [1].

Education as part of the state system requires the creation of innovative management solutions, new approaches in the training of managers, the development of personal qualities of the managerial corps in professional activities.

The topic of emotional intelligence (EI) at this time is actively developing not only in the field of psychology, but also in education. Effective personnel management is one of the most complex activities within the organization, requiring the presence of developed managerial and professional competencies, high emotional intelligence and personal charisma. It is the quality of the organization team management that determines the success of the educational organization. People are the main capital of the organization, and through their effective activity the company achieves its strategic goals. Emotional intelligence is a kind of "ability", and implies the presence of social and professional competencies that allow a person to successfully communicate and interact with others. From all of this,

it follows that emotional intelligence should be matched with competencies that are necessary for personal development and career advancement.

At the moment, educational, corporate centers or training departments are engaged in the development of the following skills that bring the greatest effectiveness to employees: Hard skills and Soft skills, which includes emotional intelligence. According to the survey of experts, in the nearest future the set of skills necessary for effective work of the employees of organizations should be renewed for more than a third in human resource management and the head of large global companies. At the same time in the list of ten basic skills of employees of the future emotional intelligence is the sixth place [2].

Materials and methods

In the sphere of management, attention should be paid to the manifestation of the emotional state of the manager, the application of certain volitional efforts to solve managerial tasks. The activity of the managerial staff of a company requires effective emotional regulation. For effective management a manager should have the following components: emotional restraint, empathy, sensitivity. The leader must be a leader, he must have a desire to act, to go forward and lead his team. At the same time it is very important for a manager to apply an individual approach to each of his employees in order to achieve the strategic goal of the company. One of the main objects of study of various activities is the study of reflexive mechanisms and emotional intelligence. Recently, the concept of emotional intelligence, as an alternative to traditional intelligence, has been widely studied in scientific circles.

Scientists from the University of Bonn Tassilo Momm and Gerhard Blicke came to the conclusion that emotional intelligence directly affects profits: employees who are better able to read feelings and emotions of their colleagues earn more. This statement was

confirmed by their experiment with 142 people - representatives of different professions and positions [3, p. 303-304].

Such facts are explained by the fact that successful people are able to interact effectively with other people based on emotional connections, and for productive professional activity it is necessary not only to generate ideas, but also to be able to present them to others. In his book "The Highwaymen" Ken Oletta quotes banker Felix Rohatyn: "Most agreements are fifty percent emotional and fifty percent economic" [3, p. 303-304].

EI is of particular importance to managers, because it takes competent and competent leadership to realize the fullest potential of employees. A leader who emotionally accommodates his team is able to influence the staff more effectively, to achieve the results he needs.

Emotional intelligence as an alternative to the traditional intellect has become widely popular in psychological and pedagogical science. This concept is in the spotlight for a reason, emotional intelligence has a good potential for practical application in addressing issues of both personal development and career growth, as well as effective management of personnel of an educational organization.

The influence and role of the emotional intelligence of an executive has been addressed by prominent foreign researchers and psychologists, such as E.L.Thorndike, J.Gilford, G.Aizenek, D.Mayer, P.Salovey, R.Caruso, D.Goleman. There is also the test of emotional intelligence, based on the ability to show the level of emotional intelligence Mayer-Salovey-Caruso Emotional Intelligence Test (Mayer-Salovey-Caruso).

Theoretical foundations of the influence and role of emotional intelligence in managers are presented in the works of domestic scientists Vygotsky L.S., Leontiev A.N., Rubinsteyn S.L., Teplov B.M. As Tikhomirov O.K. believed, emotions have a regulating function in the process of thinking, so the condition for productive intellectual activity should be emotional activation. A.V. Brushlinsky established the ambiguity of interaction between cognitive and affective processes: emotions can promote or hinder intellectual processes.

Emotional intelligence is one of the important factors of effective management in those aspects of this activity that are directly related to the phenomenon of interpersonal relationships in the organization. Thus, the analysis of the problem of emotional intelligence acquires special scientific and scientific-applied relevance in terms of the phenomenon of leadership in the organization. The effectiveness of the performance of various managerial functions by the heads of the organization is largely related to the implementation of the

latter's leadership potential. Emotional intelligence of the head of an organization, is one of the most important aspects of the leader's leadership profile. The development of this type of abilities can significantly increase the effectiveness of professional activities of management specialists. Especially its aspects that are directly related to interpersonal communication.

Many scholars argue that emotional intelligence (EI) is more important than traditional intelligence because it contributes to academic and career success, leadership skills, and mental and physical well-being [4, p. 25].

Made popular by the bestseller "Emotional Intelligence. Why It Can Mean More Than IQ" by Daniel Goleman [5, p. 41] more than 25 years ago, EI combines awareness of our emotions with the ability to use them to improve our thinking [5, p. 43].

Our ability to reason about our emotions plays a crucial role in communicating and relating to each other [5, p. 41]. Daniel Goleman suggests that high scores on traditional measures of intelligence (e.g., IQ tests) are not a reliable indicator of success outside of school. Goleman also suggests that our view of human intelligence is too limited. Instead of traditional intelligence measures, people should consider emotional intelligence (EI) when trying to understand thinking, decision-making, and personal success.

Based on research by Yale University psychologist Peter Salovey, Goleman identifies five characteristics of emotional intelligence [6, p. 110]:

1. Awareness of our emotions. We should be self-aware enough to recognize our emotions as they arise. People who are aware of their emotions are much better at managing their lives by "having a clearer picture of how they really feel about personal decisions."

2. Self-motivation. Emotional self-control is critical to "focus, self-motivation and mastery, and creativity." In addition to limiting impulsivity and delaying gratification, motivation can help us get into a state of flow and increase productivity.

3. Managing our emotions. Relying on self-awareness, it is vital that we can manage our emotions. This skill helps us cope with stress and get rid of life's inevitable difficulties.

4. Empathy. Empathy builds on our emotional self-awareness. This vital skill of working with people allows us to be aware of the needs and desires of others and can be extremely important in education, sales, and health care.

5. Relationship management skills. As Goleman states, relationships are, an art based on managing the emotions of others. Such a skill is extremely useful for our effectiveness in interpersonal relationships and supports our ability to lead and be a sought-after professional.

Figure 1 – Components of emotional intelligence

According to Larsen, more recent research suggests two models that help explain how EI works [4, p. 25]:

The ability model views EI as a receptivity that we can measure through tasks involving emotional thinking and emotional problem solving.

The mixed model of EI combines cognitive abilities with personality characteristics. It includes many non-cognitive variables, such as emotional self-efficacy, emotional regulation, and emotional dispositions.

Both models provide valuable assumptions through which to view EI and deepen our understanding of emotional awareness.

The ability to control emotions, reduce the intensity of negative emotions, realize one's emotions, including unpleasant ones, the ability to solve emotionally loaded problems without suppressing the negative emotions associated with them. Promotes personal growth and improvement of interpersonal relationships [7, p. 131].

Key features of the model include "perceiving, using, understanding, and managing emotions" [8, p. 312]. Modern researchers define emotions as cognitive, behavioral and biological reactions to our environment and personally significant events [9, p. 231].

Current developments in the field of emotional intelligence are ongoing, with many new publications focused on the role of emotional competence for organizational leaders. Daniel Goleman's mixed model, which contains such blocks as: self-awareness, control, social sensitivity, and relationship management, is very popular for describing emotional intelligence [10, p. 18-19]. This model has been criticized by some scientists, in particular G. Gardner, for its excessive psychometric bias. In psychology, the main model of emotional intelligence is the Mayer-Salovey-Caruso ability model [11]. It is this model that is most often used to describe the concept of emotional intelligence. It includes four components of emotional intelligence: perception of emotions (recognition); use of emotions to stimulate thinking; understanding of emotions (ability to understand the cause of an emotion); management of emotions.

Researchers include various aspects in the concept of emotional intelligence, including some who add elements of social intelligence to EQ.

However, there are a number of characteristics with which almost all specialists agree. The most popular technique for measuring EQ is the Hall test [12]; it

provides the most complete assessment of personality traits that characterize emotional abilities.

On the basis of this measurement technique, the authors of this article conducted a study to reveal the correspondence between the assessment of the EQ level and the results obtained in the course of the test by the respondents. Forty representatives of the personnel of three educational organizations occupying managerial (12 people) and non-managerial (28 people) positions participated in the experiment.

Before the results were announced, respondents were asked to self-assess their abilities according to five criteria: emotional awareness, managing their emotions, managing the emotions of others, empathy, and self-motivation.

Results and discussion

The main driving force of any company is people. After all, people invent things, bring interesting ideas to life, and realize the goals of the organization. That is why it is important not only to control the honesty of the employees, but also to create an environment where people are able and willing to work more productively. With this in mind, it is the manager's job to increase the interest and performance of their subordinates and to maintain an optimal atmosphere in the team. The manager should play the role of motivator and moral leader [10, p. 18-19].

According to statistics, the more interest and participation in the problems of their subordinates a manager shows, the higher the employees' satisfaction with their work. In this connection, the development of training programs for managers aimed at the development of their social and emotional competence is increasingly in demand [10, p. 18-19]. An effective leader must not only adjust his leadership style depending on the situation, but also apply a variety of skills related to emotional intelligence. By infecting the group with his enthusiasm and purposefulness, he thereby motivates the employees to work.

The results of the test are presented in Table 1, the diagram of the values of the emotional intelligence of managers and specialists is shown in Fig. 2. The comparison of the obtained EQ values allows us to conclude that the average score of the level of EQ of managers tends to a higher value. It was also revealed that among managers the percentage of respondents who objectively and critically evaluate their emotional quotient is much higher than among the rest of the employees of the organizations.

The results of the EQ level of managers and specialists

Scale name	The average value of the level of EQ of executives	The average value of the level of EQ of specialists	Maximum value of EQ level
«Emotional awareness»	14,03	11,42	18
«Managing emotions»	13,96	9,39	18
«Self-motivation»	13,42	7,85	18
«Empathy»	14,42	9,89	18
«Recognizing other people's emotions»	14,67	8,53	18
«Integrative level»	70,5	47,08	90

Figure 2. Diagram of the values of emotional intelligence of managers and specialist

Nowadays more and more attention is paid to the phenomenon of emotional intelligence. The relevance of this topic is explained by the fact that intelligence in its classical sense does not guarantee the personal and professional success of a person. Therefore, the data that are provided in the article will help to better understand what is necessary to increase emotional intelligence, and why it is so important.

In order to increase one's level of emotional intelligence, it is necessary, first of all, to understand what emotions are, where they come from, and why they are needed. Each emotion triggers certain physiological reactions in the nervous, endocrine, respiratory, digestive and other systems of the body. For example, when a person experiences anger, the blood rushes not only to the face, but also to the hands, so that he can defend himself. Only after the processes in our body provide a reaction at the level of the simplest, most basic forms of behavior does the emotion manifest itself in consciousness. The duration of an emotion does not exceed 90 seconds, after which the person decides for himself whether to prolong this state or not [13, p. 57-65].

Also, to develop EI, it is important to be able to recognize one's emotions at the beginning, since we cannot change what we do not know. It is also necessary to be able to express our feelings verbally. When a clear definition of feelings and emotions is formed in our mind, we can analyze, which will enable us to understand the cause of these reactions. It is by understanding the cause of certain emotional states that we can learn to manage them. Next, you should clearly define what you want to achieve in a given situation. Before we start to regulate our state, we should think about

what kind of relationship we want to build with the person we're talking to, maybe our natural reaction to the events (say, positive ones) will just lead to the desired effect [14, p. 197-203].

We need to be aware of how we feel, and of the impression that our feelings have on those around us. This can be learned by observing and deciphering the non-verbal "signs" of others. For example, it is not difficult to guess that if a person begins to stutter, confuse his speech, stutter, then he is nervous or afraid of something.

This study describes emotional intelligence in its broadest sense. It proves that emotional intelligence combines a person's ability to communicate effectively by understanding the emotions of others and the ability to adjust to their emotional state. This skill of self-control and the ability to organize interactions is indispensable when it comes to areas of activity that involve direct communication with others.

Awareness of our emotions-cognitive, behavioral, and biological reactions to situations and the environment in which we find ourselves-provides a large part of self-knowledge and a valuable contribution to the goals we set and how we need to work to achieve them. Being a professional with a deep understanding and appreciation of our emotions provides a vital competitive advantage; being anywhere can strengthen interpersonal relationships and improve communication with those around us.

Knowing how one reacts emotionally to a situation can help one cope with recurring or new situations in the future and maintain or regain control of one's emotions.

Conclusion

In conclusion, it can be noted that emotional intelligence, in its broadest sense, combines the ability of the individual to communicate effectively by understanding the emotions of others and the ability to adjust to their emotional state. This skill of self-control and competent organization of interaction is indispensable for spheres of activity that involve direct communication with others.

In the course of the work several methods for measuring emotional intelligence were analyzed, all of them based on the person's personal understanding of his or her own and other people's emotions. For the study, the Hall method was chosen, since it shows in the most detail the level of development on each of the components, as well as the general level of emotional intelligence. Because these techniques are based on the personal opinion of the respondent, it is worth noting that the result will be somewhat subjective. This means that the development of ways to determine the emotional intelligence is relevant today.

After receiving the test results of the respondents, the average score was calculated on the indicators of the components of emotional intelligence of employees who hold managerial positions and work directly under their control: the managers have higher scores on all indicators, indicating that emotional intelligence has a direct impact on professional success.

The main problem in improving EI is acquiring the skills to change one's emotional state in accordance with the goals set. However, when managing your emotions, it is important not to lose your sense of reality. One cannot turn a blind eye to negative situations, ignoring them will lead to more trouble; it is important to assess the situation adequately, but to choose those emotional reactions that will lead to the best result.

Thus, it is possible to build a certain sequence of reactions to an emotion, which can be followed when managing an emotional state: awareness and verbalization of the emotion and the partner emotion - formulation of the goal of the situation - determination and visualization of the emotional state in which one can achieve the greatest efficiency - choice of the method for achieving this state.

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